

MIXED NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS FOR TIME-DEPENDANT STIFFNESS DETERMINATION FOR COMPOSITE MEMBRANE UNDER BIAXIAL LOADS.

C. Szostkiewicz¹, P. Mailler², P. Hamelin¹

¹ *Laboratoire Mécanique Matériaux L2M,
Université Claude Bernard Lyon I, I.U.T. A Génie Civil,
43 boulevard du 11 novembre 1918, 69622 Villeurbanne cedex, France.*

² *Institut Textile de France Direction régionale Lyon,
avenue Guy de Collongue - BP 60 - 69132 Ecully cedex, France.*

SUMMARY:

Soft composites with textile reinforcements are used in civil engineering for roof membranes. For permanent tensile structures, it is necessary to know the response of these membranes to combined loading (multiaxial stresses, temperature...) and to be able to predict their long term behaviour. In this paper, we propose combined numerical and experiment methods to characterise this specific material with biaxial means. First, we developed a method to identify the in-plane stiffness matrix coefficients of an orthotropic composite, which is based on the results obtained from biaxial tensile tests. We then make an evaluation of the long term behaviour of the composite with rheological biaxial tests.

KEYWORDS: stiffness identification, time-dependant stiffness, biaxial tests, rheological tests, mixed methods, creep, coated fabric, textile-reinforced, tensile structures.

INTRODUCTION

Textile composites are frequently used for tensile roof structures because they offer good mechanical properties for a lesser weight. In place, these fabrics are submitted to multiaxial stresses. For that reason, but also because of interactions between warp and weft directions, monoaxial tests are no longer suitable for such structures, even if they are still widely used. Consequently, we developed a mixed numerical and experimental stiffness identification method based on a set of at least three biaxial tests. Different types of test are conducted: simple tensile test with temperature variation but also creep and relaxation tests. Then, using the time-temperature superposition principle, we are able to anticipate the evolution of the composite membrane stiffness. In this study, we mainly used a polyester fabric coated with PVC (800 g/m², 0.6 mm thick), thus it is an orthotropic material without any bending strength.

STIFFNESS IDENTIFICATION FROM BIAXIAL TESTS

Experimental set-up

Tests are carried out on large-dimensioned cross-shaped samples (1 m of wingspan and 300 mm of width) with a biaxial tension-tension apparatus, which was developed by searchers of L2M [1] & [2], in cooperation with The Institut Textile de France (Fig. 1). It can be controlled either in load or in displacement. The maximum load is 150 kN and the sample strain can reach 50 %. Large displacements are tracked by an optical measurement of the field with a CCD camera and then processed by the software Visidef. Samples are marked with dots in the central part.

A thermal enclosure makes it possible to conduct tensile, creep and relaxation tests under low or high temperatures: from -40°C to $+200^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig. 1: The L2M-ITF biaxial tensile platform with a thermal enclosure.

Stiffness Identification Method

Fig. 2: The Stiffness Identification Method principle.

The mixed numerical and experimental Stiffness Identification Method (SIM) we developed [3], was to identify the in-plane stiffness coefficient A_{ij} of a soft textile composite from biaxial test results, knowing strains in the central part of the sample and normal forces at the jaw level (Fig. 2). It is based on the mathematical solution of the inverse problem shown by

equations 1 to 3, and the evaluation of the stress distribution on the sample brought out with the FEA software Ansys.

Let us consider experimental results from a biaxial tensile test conducted in the principal directions (warp and weft):

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_1 \\ N_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{in another way :} \quad \begin{Bmatrix} N_1 \\ N_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 & \varepsilon_2 & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon_1 & \varepsilon_2 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} A_{11} \\ A_{12} \\ A_{22} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

If we now consider n experimental points taken from n different tests (conducted with various loading ratios in the warp and weft directions: 1/1, 1/2, and 2/1):

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_1^1 \\ N_2^1 \\ \dots \\ N_1^n \\ N_2^n \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1^1 & \varepsilon_2^1 & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon_1^1 & \varepsilon_2^1 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \varepsilon_1^n & \varepsilon_2^n & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon_1^n & \varepsilon_2^n \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} A_{11} \\ A_{12} \\ A_{22} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

(2n×1) (2n×3) (3×1)

This equation can be written more simply (assuming $\det({}^t[E] \cdot [E])$ is non zero):

$$\begin{aligned} \{N\} &= [E] \cdot \{A\} \\ \Rightarrow {}^t[E] \cdot \{N\} &= ({}^t[E] \cdot [E]) \cdot \{A\} \\ \Rightarrow \{A\} &= ({}^t[E] \cdot [E])^{-1} \cdot ({}^t[E] \cdot \{N\}) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 3: Global procedure for the in-plane stiffness identification.

The global procedure is described on the Fig. 3 diagram. First, we carry out a set of three biaxial tests with the different loading ratios: 1/1, 1/2 and 2/1. Using SIM, we are able to make a first rough evaluation of the stiffness, assuming that the stresses are homogeneous. With these results and information given from monoaxial tests, we can make a first evaluation of the stress distribution on the sample (FEA analysis). Then, considering the new stresses in the central part of the sample, and using the SIM, we can calculate the [A] matrix. Generally, from 3 to 5 iterations are necessary to converge.

Application

We conducted quasi-static biaxial and uniaxial tensile tests with basic loading speeds of $V = 0.2 \text{ mm/s}$ and $V = 50 \text{ N/s}$ and with different loading ratios in the warp and weft directions: 1/1, 1/2, and 2/1. The coated fabric response can be divided into three linear parts as shown on Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Biaxial test 1/2 with a loading speed of $V = 0.2 \text{ mm/s}$.

In-plane stiffness, obtained with the method we proposed above from biaxial tests, are compared to results obtained with simple uniaxial tests conducted in warp and weft directions (Fig. 5). The differences we observe, show that it is necessary to characterise these materials with biaxial means because of yarn crimps (or waves) and interactions between warp and weft directions at crossing areas.

Fig. 5: Stiffness comparison from biaxial and uniaxial tests.

RHEOLOGICAL TESTS

Quasi-static biaxial tests under high temperatures

For different temperature levels (from 25°C to 100°C, with a step of 15°C), we conducted biaxial tests with a basic loading speed of $V = 50$ N/s, and with various loading ratios. Samples are previously conditioned 15 minutes under the test temperature.

Curves for biaxial 1/1 tests at 25°C and 100°C are shown on Fig. 6. The decreasing of the stiffness clearly appears on the figure.

Fig. 6: Biaxial tensile tests at different temperatures with a loading ratio of 1/1.

Applying the stiffness identification method proposed in the first paragraph, we are able to determine the evolution with temperature of the in-plane stiffness matrix coefficients A_{11} and A_{22} corresponding to warp and weft directions, see Fig. 7.

Fig. 7: Stiffness evolution with temperature for quasi-static biaxial tests (zone II).

Thermo-stimulated biaxial creep tests

Biaxial creep tests are conducted with different loading ratios 1/1, 1/2 and 2/1, for 15 minutes. The basic load input corresponds to 30 % of the failure force for a uniaxial test in warp direction at 25°C: 3.2 kN / 300 mm of width. For instance, the ratio 1/2 means that the load is 1.6 kN / 300 mm in the warp direction and 3.2 kN / 300 mm in the weft direction.

We vary the temperature from 25°C to 115°C with a step of 15°C. The evolution of strains with time is given on figure 8 for warp and weft directions (ratio 1/1) and for different temperature levels.

Samples are previously conditioned 15 minutes under the test temperature.

We can then apply the time-temperature superposition principle (or WLF equation) [4] [5]. Creep curves made at different temperatures are superposable by horizontal shifts along a logarithmic time scale; it gives a single creep curve covering a very large range of time (master curve). The vertical correction linked to the evolution of the polymer density with temperature is neglected.

We build master curves (strain as a function of time) for each loading ratio: 1/1, 1/2 and 2/1. Curves are fitted using a logarithmic function as following [6]:

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon_0 + a \cdot \log(t/t_0) \quad \text{where } t_0 = 1 \text{ s .}$$

Fig. 8: Biaxial creep test curves with a loading ratio of 1/1.

Then, using the Stiffness Identification Method proposed in this paper, we are able to evaluate the evolution of stiffness (A_{ii} or Young's modulus) on a large scale of time. Figure 9 shows the evolution of stiffness in warp and weft directions over a 30-year period for a PVC-coated polyester fabric.

Fig. 9: Stiffness evolution with time for warp and weft directions (zone II).

Real time tests

We also conducted real time creep tests in the region of Lyon on uniaxial samples cut in warp and weft directions and with two loading levels 400 and 500 N / 300 mm, as shown on Fig. 10. After 380 days of exposure, we observe that the stiffness is reduced to about 54 % of its initial value, in both warp and weft directions.

These results are in good agreement with the evaluation made with the WLF, principle which indicates on the master curve a residual stiffness of 60 % for the same period of time.

Fig. 10: Experimental set-up for real time creep tests.

Besides, Toyoda [7] has made real time tests in Japan on polyester fabrics coated with PVC, in order to evaluate residual tensile and tearing strengths on a up to seven-year long period. He showed that the most important tensile strength loss appears in the first three years (about 50 %). The evolution up to seven years is then faint.

CONCLUSION

The stiffness evolution on short and long periods is an important parameter for the cutting pattern but also for the shape of the tensile structure. It gives an evaluation of the stress level that must be given to the membrane at the installation and, eventually, of the additional stress necessary for the structure to recover its original shape after few months or years of service.

The study we conducted makes it possible to estimate the stiffness evolution of membranes with short creep tests, and thus to improve the durability of the complete textile structure. The results we obtain, which take into account yarn crimps and interactions between warp and weft directions at crossing areas, are in good agreement with real time tests and with other studies made in literature [7].

REFERENCES

1. Bonnel P. "Modélisation géométrique et méthodes théorico-expérimentales d'identification des rigidités de composites à renforts textiles." Ph.D. Thesis, Université Claude Bernard Lyon I, 1994.
2. Mailler P. "Rhéologie des membranes composites souples orthotropes sous chargement multi-axial." Ph.D. Thesis, Université Claude Bernard Lyon I, 1996.

3. Szostkiewicz C. "Méthodes mixtes numériques et expérimentales pour la caractérisation en rigidité et la fissuration de membranes composites orthotropes." Ph.D. Thesis, Université Claude Bernard Lyon I, 1998.
4. Williams M.L., Landel R.F., Ferry J.D., Journal of the American Chemical Society, Vol. 77, 1955, pp 3701.
5. Nielsen L.E., Landel R.F. "Mechanical properties of polymers and composites." Ed. Marcel Dekker, New York, 1994.
6. Risseuw "Mechanical properties of stabilenka reinforced fabrics subjected to long term loads." ENKA, Arnhem (NL), 1982.
7. Toyoda H., Wu Y., Torii T. "Deterioration with time of the PVC-coated fabrics for tent warehouses : some experimental results." International Symposium Textile Composites In Building Construction, Part I, 23-25 june 1992, Lyon (France), Ed. Pluralis, Paris, pp 243-252.